

Why Excel Graph Paper Has Taken Root in Japan: A Historical and Cultural Background

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ABSTRACT

The Japanese language encompasses a wide variety of character types, and Japanese people input them into computers through a remarkably complex series of operations. The literacy rate in Japan today is nearly 100%. Although no definitive data exists, spreadsheet software such as Excel is widely recognized as a commonly used tool in Japanese business. Within that context, there exists a Japanese practice that surprises people from English-speaking countries: "Excel graph paper." The concept has no equivalent in English-speaking cultures, reflecting a fundamental cultural difference. This paper introduces Excel graph paper through the lens of Japan's historical and cultural background, and suggests the structural conditions under which it may arise.

Keywords: Excel graph paper, God Excel, spreadsheet, Japanese character system, word processor, kinsoku shori

1. WHAT IS EXCEL GRAPH PAPER?

Excel graph paper refers to an Excel sheet in which cells are used as a grid, cell merging is used extensively, and layouts are constructed to create long text input areas (Fig. 1).

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
1												
2												
3												
4												
5												
6												
7												
8												
9												
10												
11												
12												
13												
14												
15												
16												
17												
18												
19												
20												
21												

Fig. 1 A typical example of Excel graph paper (reproduced to resemble an actual sheet)

The most widely accepted explanation for the name is that it derives from the graph paper used when drawing by hand — the grid squares of that paper were likened to Excel cells.

2. CHARACTERISTICS

The following are the typical characteristics commonly observed:

2.1 Uniform cell width

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O
1															
2															
3	Search Engine														
4															

Fig. 2 As seen in the column headers, columns are set to a uniformly narrow width.

2.2 Cells are nearly square

6	ファイルURL
7	
8	
9	
10	Data/Time Ref

Fig. 3 Individual cells are standardized to a nearly square shape.

2.3 Merged cells present

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1										
2										
3	Search Engine									
4	検索エンジン:									
5	File URL:									
6	ファイルURL:									
7										

Fig. 4 Layout is constructed through cell merging.

3. GOD EXCEL

A related term is "God Excel" (神エクセル). The reason it is called "God" remains unclear. However, around the time the term "Excel graph paper" emerged, there was a trend in Japanese subculture of calling something impressive or overwhelming "God" — and the term may have been coined as an ironic use of that expression.

Whether the two terms refer to exactly the same thing, or are similar but distinct concepts, remains unresolved.

God Excel may include, in addition to the three characteristics above, overly complex file naming conventions, and uses of Excel that deviate from its intended purpose as spreadsheet software.

4. THE POSITION OF EXCEL GRAPH PAPER WITHIN JAPAN

In contemporary Japan, expert opinion is generally negative toward Excel graph paper. However, no explanatory framework exists to substantiate that position. Among Japanese Excel specialists, even within a single expert's own communications, the stance may shift from "prohibited" to merely "not recommended" depending on the context and stakes involved. This pattern has been observed across multiple experts.

Excel graph paper exists, and is rejected by experts, yet no supporting research, quantitative data, or formal testimony exists to justify that rejection.

When searching for "Excel graph paper" in Google Chrome in private browsing mode — eliminating the influence of personal search history — the autocomplete suggestions reveal that opinions are divided (Fig. 5, confirmed 2026-7-1 21:54).

Fig. 5 Google search autocomplete suggestions when searching for "Excel graph paper"

5. INTENDED USES OF EXCEL GRAPH PAPER

Excel graph paper falls into two broad usage patterns.

The first is the form type: survey forms and application documents that could otherwise be replaced by web forms. After downloading, users fill in the file, save it, and return it via email or similar means. The receiving party can then automate conversion into raw data with relative ease (Fig. 6). However, this is not always the case — some files are intended to be printed on a home printer and returned by fax. In such cases, one record corresponds to one sheet of paper, and ideally the layout would be created using Word's table or form features instead.

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1							年月日	
2								
3	聞き取り調査票							
4								
5				標				
6								
7							聞き取り者	
8								
9	お客様	ご氏名						
10		ご住所						
11		お電話番号						
12								
13								
14	お悩み							
15								
16								
17								
18								
19	解決へ向 けたアド バイス							
20								
21								
22								
23								
24								
25								
26								
27								
28								

Fig. 6 Example of a form-type Excel graph paper (reproduced to resemble an actual sheet)

The second is the database type: normalized raw data, lists such as change history logs, or summary reports of administrative activities compiled from raw data. Although these files contain cell merging, operations such as searching, sorting, filtering, and recalculation remain relatively straightforward after download. Here too, printing after download is sometimes an implied purpose.

The following example, while not a complete Excel graph paper structure, groups rows in column A using a character-based grouping displayed not through cell merging but through shapes. The default view is also set to page break preview, suggesting the file is intended for printing (Fig. 7, Prefectural Board of Education, 2008).

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	
1	第1表 人口規模別、教育委員会類型別の市町村教育委員会数															
2	a 委員6人制・5人制・3人制別															
3	平成19年度															
4	区分	総数	人口50万人以上	30万人以上50万人未満	10万人以上30万人未満	5万人以上10万人未満	3万人以上5万人未満	1万5千人以上3万人未満	8千人以上1万5千人未満	5千人以上8千人未満	5千人未満	全部教育事務組合	一部教育事務組合	共同設置教育委員会	広域連合教育委員会	
5	総数	計	1,932	33	49	200	281	260	327	276	172	227	-	106	1	-
6		6人制	13	13	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7		5人制	1,873	20	49	200	281	260	327	272	165	196	-	102	1	-
8	3人制	46	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	7	31	-	4	-	-	
9	市	計	782	26	45	189	277	187	54	3	1	-	
10		6人制	13	13	-	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	
11	5人制	769	13	45	189	277	187	54	3	1	-		
12	特別区	5人制	23	7	4	11	-	1	-	-	-	-	
13	町	計	825	-	-	-	3	70	268	253	138	93	
14		5人制	807	-	-	-	3	70	268	249	133	84	
15		3人制	18	-	-	-	-	-	-	4	5	9	

Fig. 7 Example of a database-type Excel graph paper

The database type can be further divided into files intended for numerical or data reuse,

and those serving as catalogue-style lists (Fig. 8). In the database type, column headers often span multiple rows, which can complicate aggregation using PivotTable features.

In the case of the Digital Agency (2023), a catalogue-type list is provided with filter buttons to improve searchability; however, due to cell merging, it is unclear whether the filters function reliably, and no official documentation exists to confirm this (Fig. 8).

項目	レベル	階層	項目名	項目説明	記述例	必須	有無	データ型	繰返し回数	備考
1	1		レスポンスオブジェクト		{	○	-	構造化	-	
2	2	metadata	レスポンスメタデータ	レスポンスについてのメタデータを格納する	"metadata": {	○	-	構造化	-	
3	3	title	タイトル	機能名称の日本語名	"title": "往來外務省名基本情報照会"	○	-	N	100	
4	3	detail	処理結果メッセージ	処理結果の日本語名	}, "detail": "照会が完了しました。"	○	-	N	10	"照会が完了しました。"固定値
5	3	counts	取得件数	取得件数	"counts": 1,	○	-	9	4	検索結果が0件の場合は、0を返す。
6	3	total	絶対条件数	検索条件の対象となる総件数	"total": 1	○	-	9	7	検索結果が0件の場合は、0を返す。 指定した取得数以上以下の場合は、取得件数と一致となる

Fig. 8 Example of a catalogue-style list

What we can observe is limited to Excel graph paper structures available on the web. Surveying actual usage rates in business settings remains difficult.

6. JAPANESE CHARACTER SYSTEM

The Japanese language contains a far greater variety of character types than English.

6.1 Characters shared with English-speaking countries:

- Alphabet (uppercase and lowercase): 26 uppercase, 26 lowercase
- Numerals: 10 characters
- Symbols (keyboard): approximately 30–40 types
- Whitespace characters: several types

6.2 Characters unique to Japanese:

- Kanji (commonly used kanji): 2,136 characters (Agency for Cultural Affairs, 2013)
- Hiragana: approximately 80 or more types
- Katakana: approximately 80 or more types
- Half-width katakana: 63 characters (generally discouraged in modern usage)
- Full-width alphabet (uppercase and lowercase): 52 characters
- Full-width symbols (keyboard): approximately 100 or more types
- Full-width whitespace characters: several types

Japanese people create documents using both characters shared with English-speaking countries and those unique to Japanese.

*Based on general knowledge of the Japanese writing system.

7. JAPANESE TEXT INPUT

In computing, "full-width" characters (全角, zenkaku) are encoded using 2 or more bytes

and occupy the width of two half-width characters on screen. "Half-width" characters (半角, hankaku) correspond to standard ASCII characters encoded in 1 byte. While English requires only one byte per character, Japanese characters such as hiragana and kanji require two or more bytes — a fundamental difference that has historically shaped the design of Japanese computing environments (Wikipedia, "Japanese language and computers", n.d.).

When Japanese people use a computer, the keyboard is inherently designed for half-width alphanumeric characters and symbols — a set far too limited for the Japanese language. As a result, users must toggle between an alphanumeric input mode and a Japanese character input mode using the "全角/半角" (full-width/half-width) key.

There are two primary input methods: kana input, where the hiragana characters printed on the keys are pressed directly, and romaji input, where hiragana is entered through sequences of one to three Roman letter keystrokes (Ministry of Education, 2011). A survey conducted on X (formerly Twitter) by Taro Kono, who was serving as Digital Minister at the time, found that romaji input is used by the overwhelming majority (Kono, 2024).

7.1 The actual input process

When entering half-width alphanumeric characters, the user simply switches to alphanumeric mode and types as in English. In Excel, pressing Enter confirms the entry into the cell.

Entering characters unique to Japanese immediately introduces far greater complexity. The following description need not be fully understood — but please pay attention to the number of steps involved.

To type a kanji character, the user switches to full-width input mode and types the hiragana reading of that kanji. For example, to type the author's name "佐藤嘉浩" in kanji: first, the surname "佐藤" is entered by mentally converting its hiragana reading "さとう" into romaji and typing "sato." This produces "さとう" on screen. Pressing the spacebar converts it to the kanji "佐藤." Pressing Enter confirms the kanji on screen. Next, the given name "嘉浩" is entered by mentally converting "よしひろ" into romaji and typing "yoshihiro," producing "よしひろ." Pressing the spacebar opens a list of kanji candidates for "ヨシヒロ" — of which there are over 100 possible combinations. The user scrolls through the candidates using the spacebar until locating "嘉浩," then presses Enter to confirm. In Excel, one additional Enter keystroke is required to confirm the entry into the cell (IBM, 2025).

Japan's internet usage rate exceeds 85% overall, with rates above 90% among those up to their 60s, and around 30% even among those aged 80 and above (Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications, 2025). In other words, the vast majority of Japanese people — from elementary school children to the elderly — perform this complex sequence of operations as a matter of daily routine, on both computers and smartphones.

It is worth imagining that Japanese people carry this cognitive and operational load in digital text input, largely without conscious awareness.

8. HISTORY OF JAPANESE WRITING

Table 1 Timeline of Japanese Writing History

Period	Event
4th–5th century	Kanji (Chinese characters) were introduced from China and subsequently developed uniquely in Japan.
8th–9th century	Hiragana emerged, and the concept of okurigana was established — a system in which hiragana syllables are appended to kanji to indicate grammatical function — analogous to how English uses auxiliary verbs such as "can" or "is" to modify the meaning of a base word.
9th–10th century	Katakana emerged and was initially used alongside or interchangeably with hiragana.
Late 19th – early 20th century (Meiji–Taisho era)	Katakana became established as the notation for loanwords, while hiragana took on the role of okurigana and native Japanese vocabulary, establishing a clear division of roles.
Around 1980	Personal computers began entering Japan, but initially could only handle characters from English-speaking countries (ASCII characters) (Iwasaki, 2011).
Early 1980s (around 1982–1983)	Personal computers capable of processing Japanese emerged, and Japanese text input environments began to take shape (Iwasaki, 2011).
Mid-1980s (around 1985)	Portable word processor dedicated machines integrated with printers entered a period of widespread adoption.
1995	Windows 95 was released, ushering in the era of one computer per household. Personal uses such as creating New Year's greeting cards became common.

9. VERTICAL WRITING CULTURE

In English-speaking countries, text is written horizontally. Japanese, by its origins, is written vertically. In the modern era, horizontal writing is also used alongside vertical (Saito, 1980).

In vertical writing, the direction of text flows not only from top to bottom, but also from right to left — another difference from English.

Fig. 9 A fictional decorative paper depicting a haiku attributed to Takarai Kikaku from the 17th century (created using Gemini)

Until the 2010s, many official government documents were written vertically. As of 2026, vertical writing is found primarily in newspaper article text, Japanese novels, Japanese textbooks, award certificates, letters of appointment, and letters of resignation. Contemporary official government documents, legal documents, and business documents are now created in A4 horizontal format.

9.1 Educational Background

In Japan, six years of elementary school beginning at age six, followed by three years of middle school, constitute compulsory education for all citizens. The academic year begins in April and ends in March of the following year.

There are three extended school holidays per year: summer vacation in and before August, winter vacation of approximately two weeks at the turn of the year, and spring vacation of approximately ten days at the turn of the academic year. The length of each holiday varies by region, reflecting optimization of fuel procurement costs due to climate differences.

Learning does not stop during these extended holidays. Homework assignments are given as tasks to be completed during each break.

Elementary school homework assignments include the following:

Assignment Type	Content and Purpose
Kanji drills	Reinforcing complex kanji through repeated writing practice
Arithmetic drills	Maintaining computational ability and logical thinking
Science free research.....	Independent inquiry through observation and investigation
Art and creative works	Cultivating artistic expression
Book reports.....	Developing reading comprehension and written self-expression

Through these efforts, in addition to regular schoolwork, Japanese people acquire mastery of a complex writing system from an early age (Otsuka & Murai, 2020).

10. MANUSCRIPT PAPER (原稿用紙)

Japanese education incorporates composition writing, such as book reports. This composition writing is also performed vertically. A standardized paper for composition

writing exists, known as genko yoshi (原稿用紙) — manuscript paper. On this manuscript paper, one character is written per cell — a concept that may strike English-speaking readers as remarkable.

Fig. 10 The Japanese draft of this paper converted to manuscript paper format using Word's manuscript paper function

Fig. 10 Word's manuscript paper conversion function

As shown above, Japanese Word includes a manuscript paper conversion feature, reflecting the needs of Japanese users (Microsoft, 2024). When this function is applied, the document is automatically converted to a vertical manuscript paper format. However, half-width alphanumeric characters are rotated 90 degrees and multiple characters share a single cell, requiring full-width character unification as a pre-processing step. Images and figures disappear in the conversion. Furthermore, this function cannot be undone (Fig. 11).

Fig. 11 manuscript paper conversion feature

11. COMPOSITION WRITING CONVENTIONS

Japanese composition writing on manuscript paper follows a set of conventions taught in elementary school (Tsubota Juku, 2025).

- Cells: One character per cell, including alphabet letters and numerals
- First line: Leave three cells blank at the top, then write the title
- Second line: Write the author's name (family name, one blank cell, given name)
- Third line: Leave blank (not always required)
- Paragraph openings: Indent one cell
- Dialogue: Enclose in 「」 quotation marks
- Punctuation: Punctuation marks are prohibited at the beginning of a line. If a punctuation mark would fall at the start of a line, it is written below the last cell of the previous line, or within the same cell as the last character of that line.
- Word breaks: Unlike English, there is no need to be conscious of word boundaries. Hyphenation is also unnecessary.

These conventions are often applied in business writing as well. In particular, it is common practice to adjust wording — substituting a word with a synonym of different character count — in order to avoid punctuation marks appearing at line beginnings, or to prevent a word or phrase from being split across lines.

12. ADVANTAGES OF MANUSCRIPT PAPER

In Japan, character count is used as a metric for written output. In handwritten manuscript paper, this character count is easy to visualize. A rough estimate can be obtained by multiplying the number of sheets by the number of rows and columns of cells per sheet. For a more precise count, the number of blank cells per sheet can be subtracted from this estimate.

Character count is currently used as a metric in the following contexts: compulsory education composition assignments, university thesis and assignment documents, corporate apology statements, and outsourced blog article fees, which are calculated as character count × unit price per character.

At the university level in particular, assignments are sometimes submitted on paper, in which case character counting by the instructor is made easier by the manuscript paper format (Wikipedia, n.d.-a).

13. TRANSITION TO HORIZONTAL WRITING

Given the historical background described above, even in the modern era where business documents are created horizontally on a PC, the culture of one character per cell tends to remain deeply embedded. When the character directly below does not align with the one above, a sense of discomfort arises — a deviation from the foundational principle of Japanese typesetting known as *kihon hanmen* (基本版面), which prescribes uniform placement of square character frames (Grokopedia, n.d.).

This creates a cultural environment in which proportional fonts, as used in English, are inherently unwelcome.

Although proportional fonts exist for Japanese, characters other than half-width alphanumeric and symbols are effectively fixed-width. When a Japanese proportional font is used and half-width alphanumeric characters are mixed with Japanese characters, a vertical misalignment occurs between characters on adjacent lines. Even though the meaning remains readable, this misalignment becomes a greater source of distraction than the content itself.

Fig. 12 Proportional fonts (top) and fixed-width fonts (bottom)

14. THE DIFFICULTY OF MICROSOFT WORD IN JAPANESE

In Japan, Microsoft Word (hereafter Word) is perceived as a "word processor" — a tool for creating clean, formatted documents, in the tradition of dedicated word processor machines (Kojikoji, 2026).

The author personally found Word completely unusable upon first encounter. The reason was simple: it was not possible to place the cursor anywhere on the page. To move the cursor to a given position, text had to already exist up to that point, preceded by a paragraph. On dedicated word processor machines, moving the cursor to any position on the screen allowed immediate text entry at that location. As a result, dedicated word processors were typically used in overwrite mode (Wikipedia, n.d.-b). This is fundamentally at odds with Word's behavior.

Word was not developed in Japan. It was designed for English-speaking users entering alphanumeric characters. Beyond its purpose of creating clean documents, it was also intended as an outline document processor — a tool for structurally organizing and flexibly shaping the meaning and ideas within a text. In Japan, however, it has generally been used solely for creating visually polished documents. Even today, the author personally closes documents created for printing purposes without saving them.

In addition to the proportional font issues described earlier, Word has its own set of features designed to improve readability:

- Font settings: Kerning
- Paragraph settings: Adding spacing between full-width and half-width characters
- Bullets and numbering: Automatic insertion of tab characters
- Kinsoku shori (禁則処理): When examined in Microsoft's official documentation (Microsoft Learn Community, 2011), the equivalent feature in the English version of

Word is explicitly categorized under a separate "Asian Typography" tab in the Paragraph dialog box, labeled "Use Asian rules for controlling first and last characters" — an acknowledgment by Microsoft itself that this is an Asia-specific typographic rule set. This active line-spacing adjustment to prevent punctuation from appearing at line beginnings disrupts the uniform character alignment that Japanese readers expect.

- Justification: In addition to left alignment, full justification is available

Each of these features disrupts the structure in which the character directly below aligns with the character above — a fundamental expectation in Japanese typesetting.

Word was designed as a structured document processor (Zachary, 1994). In Japan today, however, Word is positioned as software that exists on the computer for the purpose of creating documents, used out of necessity rather than preference (Kojikoji, 2026). The domestic word processing software "Ichitaro" held the top market share in Japan before Word's arrival. Because Ichitaro was less prone to these issues, it retains a degree of support even as of 2026.

15. WHY DID WORD BECOME JAPAN'S STANDARD WORD PROCESSING SOFTWARE?

Despite being functionally disliked, Word became Japan's standard word processing software because Microsoft proposed to Japanese PC manufacturers that PCs pre-installed with Microsoft Office be sold as a bundle with Windows 95 (Japan Fair Trade Commission, 1998).

Before Windows 95, the NEC PC-98 series held an overwhelmingly dominant share of the Japanese home PC market. EPSON also sold compatible machines. This PC-98 compatible market was the foundation.

Even when Windows 95 was released, the NEC PC-98 remained dominant. At that point, Microsoft proposed to NEC and other Japanese PC manufacturers that pre-installing Microsoft Office would allow PCs to be sold at a lower price, while also offering users the benefit of a computer ready to use straight out of the box, simply by plugging it in.

A model in which hardware, OS, and applications were sold as a single package became established (Wikipedia, n.d.-c).

Ichitaro continued to ship pre-installed on some models in the early years, but as Microsoft made Word and Excel a mandatory bundle for PC manufacturers — a practice later found to violate Japan's Antimonopoly Act (Japan Fair Trade Commission, 1998) — Ichitaro gradually disappeared from pre-installed offerings. The founder of JustSystems, the developer of Ichitaro, later stated: "Windows-based PCs were required to have Excel and Word pre-installed. This effectively made it impossible for PC manufacturers to sell PCs bundled with Ichitaro." (Nikkei Business, 2023)

This structure has persisted to the present day in 2026, even as PC manufacturers have diversified far beyond NEC. As a result, most Japanese people have the perception that Word and Excel naturally come with any PC they purchase.

Paradoxically, this means a PC without Microsoft Office is considered unattractive. For this reason, Microsoft's own PC hardware, the Surface Pro series, comes with Microsoft Office pre-installed exclusively in the Japanese market. Models without Office pre-installed do not exist in the Japanese market. As can be seen by comparing the Japanese

Surface Pro product page (Microsoft, n.d.-a) with the US equivalent (Microsoft, n.d.-b), Office pre-installation is unique to the Japanese market.

16. CONNECTION TO EXCEL GRAPH PAPER

Given the historical and cultural background described above, the hypothetical routes leading to Excel graph paper are wide-ranging. It should be noted that all of them are ambiguous and cannot be proven. Furthermore, there is no evidence that the historical and cultural background described above is actually the cause.

The most that can be said is that a historical and cultural background exists as the highest plausible explanation.

As of 2026, the oldest known web article referencing Excel graph paper dates to 2009. However, it remains unknown from what point prior to that this structure existed.

At the time when vertical writing and manuscript paper already existed, the first spreadsheet software, VisiCalc, also existed. At that point, Japanese people who encountered VisiCalc were in a situation where it could have appeared to them as manuscript paper with one character per cell.

As of 2026, the existence of Excel graph paper is a fact. The inefficiency of entering one character per cell was circumvented by the introduction of the cell merging feature. Nevertheless, even today, Excel file templates distributed for download by government agencies include formats in which code numbers or certain numerical values are entered one character per cell.

銀行 信用金庫 農協									本店 支店 出張所
当座預金	口座番号								

Fig. 13 Bank transfer request form (Chofu City, 2023)

This is all that can be stated as fact at this time.

17. HISTORY OF EXCEL GRAPH PAPER

The following is a timeline of events related to Excel graph paper as of June 30, 2026.

From 2016 to 2026, the actions of Taro Kono — serving as a member of the Diet and later as Minister for Digital Transformation — form one axis of this timeline.

Table 2. Timeline of events related to Excel graph paper

Date	Event
Around 2000	Excel begins to be used frequently in Japanese workplaces following the shift to Windows
November 4, 2009	Oldest known web reference (Mynavi News, 2009)
March 10, 2013	Togetter summary related to "ネ申 Excel" (Okumura, 2013)
May 2013	Nikkei WOMAN Web article recommending Excel graph paper; online criticism of the article (Okumura, 2013)
August 2013	Publication of "ネ申 Excel Problem" paper (Information Education Symposium 2013). Academic formalization (Okumura, 2013)
November 2, 2016	Diet member Taro Kono raises concerns on X about Excel graph paper in research grant applications. Instructs the Ministry of Education to abolish the practice (Kono, 2016)
September 30, 2017	GrapeCity-hosted [1] Excel graph paper public debate [2] (Nikkei Cross Tech, 2017)
December 18, 2020	Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications establishes "Unified Rules for Machine-Readable Data Notation in Statistical Tables" (Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications, 2020) [3]
September 1, 2021	Digital Agency established (Digital Agency, 2021)
August 10, 2022	Taro Kono appointed as Minister for Digital Transformation (Digital Agency, 2022)
Around October 2022	Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications' metaverse public comment solicitation form draws criticism for using Excel graph paper format; Minister Kono issues clarification (Kono, 2022)
2023	Despite Minister Kono's tenure, Digital Agency API specification confirmed to be in God Excel format (Digital Agency, 2023)
October 1, 2024	Minister Kono's press conference upon leaving office (Digital Agency, 2024)
2026	Digital Agency API specification continues in God Excel format (Digital Agency, 2026)

[1] GrapeCity (now MESCIUS, <https://developer.mescius.jp/>) provides a no-code application development solution called "Forguncy." The product name Forguncy was named for its phonetic resemblance to the Japanese word for graph paper, houganshi (方眼紙), as directly confirmed by Yuya Yamaki of GrapeCity (now MESCIUS) (Y. Yamaki, personal communication, ca. 2015). The exact date of this communication was not recorded.

[2] The debate over whether "Excel graph paper" and "God Excel" are the same concept or distinct ones ended without resolution, concluding instead with a sense of shared enthusiasm among participants.

[3] This document was addressed to government agencies nationwide. It was the first official document to compile normative guidelines for spreadsheet usage. While not directly targeting Excel graph paper itself, it recommends data normalization primarily aimed at God Excel practices.

Fig. 14 Cover sheet of the 住登外者宛名基本情報照会 API specification: a form that fits neither the form type nor the database type (Digital Agency, 2023)

18. CASES OUTSIDE JAPAN

While not typical examples, Excel sheets with layouts adjusted through cell merging can be downloaded from government and administrative websites in the United States, the United Kingdom, the EU, and elsewhere.

None of these clearly exhibit the Excel graph paper structure as defined in this paper. However, when the quality of spreadsheets published on official government and administrative websites is evaluated from the perspectives of both security and auditability, their reliability must be considered low.

The purpose of introducing these cases is limited to demonstrating that this is not a phenomenon unique to Japan.

18.1 Files with Excel graph sheet structure outside Japan

1.1.1 White House

At first glance, the file appears to be a simple text-heavy table. However, row 1 is entirely merged across all columns. Searching Google for "Good Accounting Obligation in Government Act Report for Fiscal Year 2026 Budget Justification Submission" returns the file itself, titled "Sheet1" (White House, 2026).

Report Title	Report Number	Issue Date	Audit Area	GAO Recommendation	Bureau/Office	Implementation Status
Information Management: Selected Agencies Need to Fully Address Federal Electronic Recordkeeping Requirements	GAO-20-59	2020/2/27	Information Management	The Director of the Office of National Drug Control Policy should establish a time frame to develop an inventory of electronic information systems used to store agency records that includes all of the required elements.	ONDCP	PCA Due Date: September 2025
Information Management: Selected Agencies Need to Fully Address Federal Electronic Recordkeeping Requirements	GAO-20-59	2020/2/27	Information Management	The Director of the Office of National Drug Control Policy should establish a time frame to ensure, in conjunction with the Office of Administration, that policies and procedures include the (1) following records management controls required for electronic information systems: reliability, content, and structure; and (2) required preservation mechanisms to ensure that records in its electronic recordkeeping system will be retrievable and useable.	ONDCP	PCA Due Date: September 2025
Information Management: Selected Agencies Need to Fully Address Federal Electronic Recordkeeping Requirements	GAO-20-59	2020/2/27	Information Management	should ensure, in conjunction with the Office of Administration, that existing policies and procedures include the required retention and management requirements for email.	ONDCP	PCA Due Date: September 2025
Drug Control: The Office of National Drug Control Policy Should Develop Key Planning Elements to Meet Statutory Requirements	GAO-20-124	2019/12/18	Administration of Program Operations	The Director of ONDCP should—after developing and documenting key planning elements to meet the SUPPORT Act requirements—routinely implement an approach, based on these planning elements, to meet the requirements for the 2020 National Drug Control Strategy and future Strategy planning.	ONDCP	Implemented and Awaiting GAO Verification
Drug Control: The Office of National Drug Control Policy Should Develop Key Planning Elements to Meet Statutory Requirements	GAO-20-124	2019/12/18	Administration of Program Operations	documenting key planning elements—implement an approach, based on these planning elements, to meet the SUPPORT Act requirements to establish a Drug Control Data Dashboard.	ONDCP	Implemented and Awaiting GAO Verification

Fig. 15 Example from the White House

1.1.2 UK Government

While there is no explicit cell merging, the data structure does not permit sorting. Searching Google for "Percentage of employee jobs in high and medium technology industries" returns the file itself, titled "C(3)" (GOV.UK, 2010).

RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT, AND EMPLOYMENT IN HIGH AND MEDIUM-HIGH TECHNOLOGY INDUSTRIES																
Table C(3) - Numbers and Percentages of Total Employee Jobs in the High and Medium High Technology Sectors																
Thousands and per cent	United Kingdom ¹	GO Region/Country														
		North East	North West	Yorkshire and the Humber	East Midlands	West Midlands	East of England	London	South East	South West	Greater South East	North, Midlands & West	England	Wales	Scotland	Northern Ireland ²
1998 level	1,518	75	190	114	125	220	150	75	214	129	439	854	1,292	77	117	32
per cent	6.1	8.0	6.8	5.6	7.1	9.6	6.8	2.0	6.3	6.6	4.7	7.2	6.1	7.4	5.4	5.2
1999 level	1,462	68	187	106	115	206	133	77	218	126	428	808	1,236	81	114	32
per cent	5.7	7.1	6.6	5.1	6.7	8.9	6.2	1.9	6.1	6.3	4.4	6.8	5.7	7.6	5.2	5.1
2000 level	1,436	68	181	105	113	192	139	72	211	127	422	786	1,208	78	115	35
per cent	5.6	7.1	6.3	5.0	6.5	8.4	6.2	1.8	5.8	6.2	4.2	6.6	5.5	7.3	5.1	5.4
2001 level	1,365	66	176	102	110	184	136	66	192	124	394	762	1,156	71	103	34
per cent	5.2	6.7	6.1	4.8	6.3	8.0	6.0	1.6	5.2	5.9	4.0	6.3	5.2	6.5	4.5	5.3
2002 level	1,279	64	163	96	103	176	132	57	183	113	372	715	1,087	69	91	32
per cent	4.9	6.4	5.5	4.4	5.9	7.6	5.8	1.5	5.0	5.3	3.8	5.8	4.9	6.3	4.0	4.9
2003 level	1,180	57	153	91	99	160	114	48	172	108	333	669	1,002	67	80	30
per cent	4.5	5.7	5.1	4.1	5.6	6.9	4.9	1.2	4.7	5.0	3.4	5.4	4.5	6.0	3.5	4.5
2004 level	1,132	54	148	86	93	148	108	48	163	107	318	636	955	69	79	29
per cent	4.2	5.4	4.8	3.7	5.2	6.3	4.6	1.3	4.4	4.8	3.2	5.0	4.2	6.0	3.3	4.3
2005 level	1,087	55	136	82	97	139	107	43	154	101	304	610	914	66	78	29
per cent	4.0	5.2	4.6	3.7	5.2	5.8	4.5	1.0	4.1	4.6	3.0	4.8	4.0	5.6	3.2	4.1
2006 level	1,051	54	134	81	93	129	102	40	151	102	292	593	885	61	76	29
per cent	3.9	5.2	4.4	3.6	5.0	5.4	4.3	1.0	4.1	4.6	2.9	4.7	3.9	5.2	3.2	4.1
2007 level	1,037	53	132	82	94	124	104	38	152	98	294	581	875	62	71	29
per cent	3.8	5.2	4.3	3.6	4.9	5.2	4.4	0.9	4.1	4.4	2.9	4.5	3.8	5.2	3.0	4.0
2008 level	999	51	121	80	88	123	105	35	142	95	282	558	840	61	68	29
per cent	3.6	4.9	4.0	3.6	4.7	5.2	4.4	0.8	3.8	4.2	2.7	4.4	3.6	5.2	2.8	4.0

Fig. 16 Example from the UK Government

1.1.3 Official EU

Explicit cell merging is present, and clicking a shape triggers a macro. The file extension is .xls (EU, 2021).

Fig. 17 Example from the official EU website

1.1.4 WHO

A form-type Excel graph paper variant. Searching Google for "REQUEST FOR ADDITIONAL ANTI-LEPROSY MEDICINE SUPPLY" returns the file itself, titled "NPM Quarterly Reports" (WHO, 2013).

COUNTRY:		Request Year:					
		MB PATIENTS		PB PATIENTS			
		ADULT	CHILD	ADULT	CHILD		
Additional number of cases to be treated by MDT*							
Number of cases registered* (at test available data)		Date					
<p>* As WHO provides both adult and child blister packs, please provide a breakdown by the type of case. Please indicate the number of additional cases that have already registered or will be found until the end of the supply year (from July to June of every year). Please give more details in support of the additional request in the field dedicated to the remarks. Please note that additional drug supply is not preliminary planned and in some cases additional drugs cannot be dispatched immediately. Delivery lead time is hardly predictable and, depending on the situation (specific country requirements, requested amount, state of emergency etc.), it may vary from 2 weeks up to 6 months. Thus WHO encourages countries to plan detection campaigns and other important activities, that can impact the trend, in advance and to share it with WHO within the scope of the annual request.</p>							
STOCKS**		MB Blisters		PB Blisters		CLOFAZIMINE	
		ADULT	CHILD	ADULT	CHILD	50 mg	100 mg
CENTRAL LEVEL STOCKS		10					

Fig. 18 Example from WHO

18.2 Concepts Similar to Excel Graph Sheets

1.1.5 "Franken-sheet"

A related concept is the "Franken-sheet" — an internet slang term referring to a worksheet that has become extremely complex and unstable after years of modifications by multiple users who have continuously added macros and complex formulas, resulting in a state where no one other than the original creator can understand its structure, and users can only "pray it doesn't break" (SafeBooks AI, n.d.).

1.1.6 "Code smells in spreadsheets"

Prior research has documented cases in which formula structures and cell references become bloated through continued use, resulting in loss of readability, as described in research on code smells in spreadsheets (Jansen & Hermans, 2015).

1.1.7 "Spreadsheet Hell"

The broader context for these international cases is the concept of "Spreadsheet Hell" — a term used within the EuSpRIG community to describe the organizational and technical dysfunction arising from uncontrolled spreadsheet use. According to research cited by EuSpRIG, 60% of large companies feel "Spreadsheet Hell" describes their reliance on spreadsheets either completely or fairly well.

Spreadsheet Hell can be considered on two levels: at the micro level, it refers to "Frankensheets" — big, ugly spreadsheet monsters that are hard to understand, hard to use and hard to test. At the macro level, regardless of the quality of individual spreadsheets, the way those spreadsheets are used, shared and replicated creates a whole other level of spreadsheet risk (Murphy, 2007).

The cases presented below — from the White House, UK Government, EU, and WHO — are not examples of Frankensheets or formula errors in the traditional EuSpRIG sense. Rather, they represent a different dimension of spreadsheet risk: the absence of auditability and the normalization of insecure distribution practices at the institutional level. In this sense, Excel graph paper as observed in Japan, and the broader Spreadsheet Hell as documented by EuSpRIG, share a common root: **the structural interaction between spreadsheet software and human behavior produces problematic outcomes universally, regardless of cultural context.**

19. LIMITATIONS OF THE RESEARCH

Specific prior research on Excel graph paper is limited to works such as Okumura (2013), and the field remains largely unexplored.

The merits and demerits of Excel graph paper exist, but they shift so easily depending on the situation that no axis of judgment for good or evil can be established.

The psychological background that gives rise to Excel graph paper is unlikely to emerge through surveys. Even if respondents report having been taught to use it by someone, tracing the practice back to its origin would be impossible. Furthermore, the very question "Why do you use Excel graph paper?" contains an implicit negation of the practice, introducing bias into responses.

It is difficult to determine the absolute prevalence of the phenomenon. Excel files may constitute confidential data within companies and organizations.

Similarly, while the term "misuse" is applied to Excel in common discourse, the correct use of Excel — which would serve as the basis for defining misuse — has not been defined. As a result, neither denial, affirmation, nor criticism of the practice is possible.

A further limitation of this paper is that, while Excel usage has been categorized into two types — form type and database type — the criteria for these categories have not yet been fully defined, making complete classification impossible. Cases such as the cover

sheet of the Digital Agency's API specification, which uses cell merging solely for the cover page, cannot be classified under either type.

What can be said in conclusion is that Excel graph paper is not entirely negative. While it may appear unusual, from an HCI perspective it offers advantages in readability. When its features are used appropriately, it can also offer significant benefits as a form input tool that minimizes errors and enables downstream processing.

Finally, the possibility that the use of spreadsheet software universally tends toward Excel graph paper-like usage patterns when employed by human beings also warrants further verification from the perspective of the structural interaction between spreadsheet characteristics and human cognition and cultural background.

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Appendix: Excel Graph Paper Score Sheet Manual

1. WORKBOOK-LEVEL ATTRIBUTES / ブックごとの属性

1.1 Search Engine / 検索エンジン

Search engine used for the search / 検索に使った検索エンジン

Example: DuckDuckGo

1.2 Search Query / 検索クエリ

Search keywords / 検索ワード

Example: "ダウンロード.xls" ("Download.xls") Input in Japanese

1.3 File URL

Example: https://www.cas.go.jp/jp/seisakukaigi/titeki2/keiei_design/files/siryou1.xlsx

1.4 Source Page URL / 元ページ URL

Example: https://www.cas.go.jp/jp/seisakukaigi/titeki2/keiei_design/index.html

1.5 Is a PDF of the same file distributed on the source page? / 元ページに同じファイルの PDF を配布しているか

The site also distributes Excel files converted to PDF. [Yes or No] / Excel ファイルを PDF に変換したのもも配布しているか [Yes or No]

1.6 Date/Time Retrieved / 取得日時

Example: 2026-6-28 22:38

1.7 Document Name / 書類名

Example: 全社シート（複数事業会社等向け） / Company-wide Sheet (for multiple business companies, etc.)

1.8 Institution Name / 機関名

Example: 内閣官房 / Japanese Cabinet Secretariat

1.9 File name / ファイル名

Example: siryou1.xlsx

2. SHEET-LEVEL CHARACTERISTICS / シートごとに見られる特徴

The judgment is basically [Yes or No]. / 判定は、基本的に [Yes or No]

2.1 [Layout-related] / 【レイアウト系】

2.1.1 Uniform cell width / セル幅統一

Column widths are the same, and all values except the default are standardized / 列幅がデフォルト値以外の同じ幅で統一されている。変更時困難。

undesirable

2.1.2 Cells are nearly square / セルがほぼ正方形

Individual cells are standardized to a nearly square shape, making layout changes difficult. / 1 個 1 個のセルが正方形に近い。変更時困難。

undesirable

2.1.3 Merged cells present / セル結合あり

Numerous cell merges are present, making layout changes difficult. / セル結合が多い。変更時困難。

undesirable

2.2 [Forms/Reporting-related] / 【帳票系】

2.2.1 Single record only / 1 レコードのみ

The sheet contains only a single record and functions as an input form. Word documents or web forms would be more appropriate; there is no need for Excel format. / 1 レコードのみの帳票、形式が入力フォームになっており、Word 作成や Web フォーム活用などが望ましい。Excel 形式である必要がない。

undesirable

2.2.2 One record spans multiple lines / 複数行で1 レコード

A single record spans multiple rows, making aggregation and sorting difficult. / 1 レコードが複数行に渡っている。集計、並べ替えの困難性。

undesirable

2.2.3 Number of sheets in file (Count) / ファイル内のシート枚数 (数)

The number of sheet tabs visible simultaneously on one screen is limited, so fewer sheets are preferable. / 1 画面でのシート見出しの同時表示数には限りがあるため、少ない方が望ましい。

less is preferable

2.2.4 Number of blank sheets (Count) / 空白シート枚数 (数)

Blank sheets are wasteful. / 空白シートは無駄である。

less is preferable

2.2.5 Default Sheet name / デフォルトシート名

The sheet name remains as "Sheet1," making it impossible to infer the content from the sheet name. / シート名が Sheet1 のままになっており、シート名から内容が推察できない。

undesirable

2.2.6 Select by shape / 図形で選択する

Selections are shown in shapes rather than inputs / 選択が入力ではなく図形で示すようになっており、選択肢がデータで取得できない

undesirable

2.2.7 Adding text to numeric cells / 数値セルに文字追加

The numeric cells contain units and notes / 数値のセルに単位や注意書きがあり、数値としてではなく文字として認識されている。

undesirable

2.2.8 All cells write-protected / 全セル書き込み禁止

Writing to cells is prohibited, and entry cannot be enabled because the protection cannot be removed. In such cases, the only option is to print the file and write on it manually. / セルに書き込み禁止され、解除できないために入力不可になっている場合、印刷したものに書き込むしか方法がない。

undesirable

2.3 [Input Assistance-related] / 【入力支援系】

2.3.1 Protected / 保護あり

Proper sheet protection / 不必要な箇所には入力、変更ができないように、シート保護が適切

desirable

2.3.2 Protected with password / 保護+パスワード

Proper sheet protection and password protection / シート保護が適切かつパスワードで保護されており、必要ではない箇所がより強力に不必要な箇所には入力、変更ができないようになっている

desirable

2.3.3 Indented and evenly distributed in the space / スペースでインデント、均等割り付け

The layout is adjusted using spaces. Including cases where line breaks within cells are inappropriate. In such cases, the keyword cannot be found using the search function. / レイアウトがスペースで調整されている。セル内改行が不適切な場合も含む。この場合、検索機能でそのキーワードが検索できなくなる。

undesirable

2.3.4 Data validation rules / 入力規則あり

Data validation provides list selection, input restrictions, and input guidance, making the form user-friendly. / 入力規則でリスト選択、入力値制限、入力時案内があり、親切である。

desirable

2.3.5 Conditional formatting / 条件付き書式あり

Conditional formatting enables validation of input values, allowing users to notice input errors at the time of entry. / 条件付き書式で入力値の検証ができ、入力時に入力ミスに気付ける。

desirable

2.4 [Digitization Trace-related] / 【デジタル化痕跡系】

2.4.1 Filter buttons / フィルターボタンあり

Filters are configured, indicating that the sheet is intended for use as a database. / フィルターが設定してあり、データベースとして使うことが前提になっている。

desirable

2.4.2 Table present / テーブルあり

A table is defined for the cell range, indicating that the sheet is intended for use as a database. / セル範囲にテーブルが設定されており、データベースとして使うことが前提になっている。

desirable

2.4.3 Formulas present / 計算式あり

Formulas reduce the need for manual data entry. / 計算式により、手入力の手間が省かれている。

desirable

2.4.4 Non-standard default view / デフォルト表示が標準以外

The default view is set to page layout or page break preview rather than normal view, indicating that the sheet is intended for printing. / 標準以外のページレイアウトや改ページプレビューになっており、印刷として使うことを前提としている。

undesirable

2.5 [Security-related] / 【セキュリティ系】

2.5.1 Residual properties / プロパティ残存

The presence of file creator names, organization names, or other administrative metadata may introduce bias during data entry. / ファイルの作成者や組織、余計な事務情報があることで、入力時にバイアスがかかる可能性がある。

undesirable

2.5.2 File located at root / ファイル直置き

The file has no linking source page and can be downloaded directly from search results. In such cases, a file containing embedded macros can be downloaded as-is, making it a potential security risk. / リンク元なし、ファイルのダウンロードが検索結果から直でできる。この場合、マクロ混入ファイルをそのままダウンロードできるだけ、セキュリティリスクになりやすい。

undesirable

2.5.3 .xls extension / 拡張子 XLS

The .xls format is outdated. In addition to being unable to use the latest features, it increases the risk of virus infection. / 拡張子が.xls で形式が古く、最新機能が使えないだけでなく、ウイルス感染の可能性も広がる。

undesirable

2.5.4 Formulas editable / 計算式変更可能

If formulas can be overwritten or modified, the user may replace them with formulas of their own choosing. / 計算式を上書き、変更ができる場合、入力者が自分の意図の計算式に変更できてしまう。

undesirable